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The Effect of Student Self-Reflection using a Learner Disposition Matrix on Student
Achievement and Attitude in Math and Art

Action Research

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Abstract

Forty-three 6th grade math and art students attending the American School of Dubai participated in an action research study exploring the question, “What is the effect of student self-reflection using a Learner Disposition Matrix on student achievement and attitude in math and art?” A two-group pre/post test design measured student achievement on formal assessments over six weeks. The experimental group consisted of one 6th grade math class and one 6th grade art class who were given dedicated class time once per week to self-reflect on dispositional skills. The reflections were based on guided questions derived from the American School of Dubai’s “Learner Development” rubric and their responses were recorded on each student’s personal eportfolio. The comparison group consisted of one 6th grade math class and one 6th grade art class and they were not given the class time for self-reflection. The two groups scores on assessments and report cards were compared between the beginning and end of the six-week treatment period. Results indicated that the mean scores on formal assessments in art class were better than the control group after six weeks, while the math groups showed no significant difference.

The Effect of Student Self-Reflection Using a Learner Disposition Matrix on Student
Achievement and Attitude in Math and Art

At the very core of American education, is the importance of educating the whole child. Teaching a subject area, isn't just about teaching content, but instead is inclusive of important disposition, character, and performance skills that lead to success inside and outside of the content. Our own school, the American School of Dubai, has recently integrated a "Learner Development Rubric" (see Appendix A) containing 20 cross-content character, habit, and performance skills.

We see examples elsewhere in nationwide initiatives such as The Common Core State Standards in Mathematics, which have eight "Standards for Mathematical Practice" spanning all grade levels and including skills such as perseverance, the ability to communicate, and appropriate use of resources (Common Core State Standards). University emblems often emphasize moral or character values: Florida State University's emblem states *vires, artes, mores*, meaning *strength, skill, character*; New York University's motto is *Perstare et praestare*, meaning *to persevere and to excel*; and our own undergraduate alma-mater of UW Eau Claire's emblem proclaims *excellence*. Primary and Secondary schools often advertise a set of shared

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values and the American School of Dubai, has recently adopted a set of five “core values” comprised of *respect, integrity, compassion, excellence, and responsibility*.

This desire for teaching character traits, is not restricted only to the current era. Althof and Berkowitz state:

...this field has existed as long as humans have thought about how to raise each subsequent generation. Classic thinkers, like Aristotle and Confucius, have reflected in depth upon the questions central to [this] field; i.e. what kind of person do we want each of our children to be and how can we raise and educate them to be that way? (Althof, & Berkowitz, 2006, p.496).

In John Dewey’s formative text *Democracy and Education*, first published in 1916, Dewey states that education prepares students for “...the responsibilities and privileges of adult life” (Dewey, 2007, p.45). In the present day, the United States Department of Education includes character education within its best practices, and in Witt and Orvis’s *A Guide to Becoming a School of the Future*, skills such as attentive listening, counseling others, collaboration, open-mindedness, integrity, and ethics are listed as essential capacities for the 21st century (Orvis, & Witt, 2010).

In our respective fields (math & art), we have casually observed that certain dispositions seemingly lead to more success with in our content areas. Students more willing to complete homework with care and persevere through difficulties by seeking the appropriate assistance seem to find more success in mathematics. In the visual arts students who are able to demonstrate independence and conscientiousness towards the task at hand, seem to find more

success as well. Therefore one of our own goals, aligning with our school's goals, is to increase capacity within this range of skills.

Given the seemingly ubiquitous importance of character/moral/disposition education, as well as the recent abundance of data-driven achievement markers, we sought to design a study to attempt to align character education goals with academic achievement. We believe that if students are allowed to increase their own competence around these skill sets, then they would also see improved academic achievement. Our hypothesis was if students are given time to reflect on dispositional and developmental strategies, the increased self-awareness would lead to improved character and performance skills and therefore increase their academic achievement as well. The following study was designed to explore this hypothesis.

Review of Literature

As stated before, there has been a collective importance on teaching values for a long time. However, the names of these skills have also changed. The American School of Dubai uses "Learner Development" while other schools may use "Dispositions." It is important for this study to understand that we are using the terms *Character Education*, *Values*, *Dispositions*, *Learner Development*, etc. interchangeably. All of them are being used to describe the set of "soft skills" that support rather than make up the curriculum. They include study habits, morals, social and emotional skills, attitude, and self-regulatory skills.

We have enough evidence to show that students *possessing* these skills will have more academic success. John Hattie's text has created a "meta of meta's" bringing together and

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ranking 138 educational influences. After the results came in, a student's own *concentration/persistence/engagement* ranked #49 and their *motivation* followed closely behind ranked #51, both influences having a positive effect of 0.48 – that is to say that students who carried these traits increased their aptitude by 0.48 of a standard deviation. Other skills that showed positive gain were self-concept, reducing anxiety, attitude, and personality (Hattie, 2009).

Another series of meta-analyses in *Classroom Instruction that Works* ended with ten classroom strategies as most significant for improving learning. Included in the list are practice, note taking, and cooperative learning (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001). It is therefore not a distant conclusion that skills that predispose students to success within those classroom structures – such as those listed in John Hattie's meta analyses – would lead to higher academic achievement.

We also need to explore whether programs and initiatives that are intended to improve these skills correlate to higher academic achievement. A study of 120 schools in the state of California showed small but significant positive correlations on the SAT9 score when a school had more character education implementation. Percentage of students scoring above the 50th percentile in Reading, Language, and Math also increased by 3, 3.8, and 6.1 percent respectively (Beninga, Berkowitz, Kuehn, & Smith, 2003).

Another study done over 4 years in 5 different districts came to a different conclusion. The results stated, "Character education programming had little impact on student achievement, perhaps because of the lack of a direct relationship between character education goals and student achievement goals." (Bodenhorn, & Skaggs, 2006, p.83). Also important to note is that

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both the Beninga et al. study and the Bodenhorn & Skaggs study, concluded that high levels of character education implementation led to significant increases on perceived character skills within their student population (Beninga et al., 2003).

Looking back at the *Visible Learning* meta-analyses, teaching a study skills course ranked 25th of the 138 influences and having a social skills program ranked 65th – with effects of 0.59 and 0.40 on academic achievement respectively (Hattie, 2009). Even with these meta-analyses and rankings, the text is still a bit nebulous as to whether or not offering time to improve soft skills in a content specific class improved academic achievement.

Therein lies our problem. We can specifically point to research that shows that the presence and utilization of these skills improves learning, but how do we actually go about making individual improvements? In *Character Education Re-Conceptualized for Practical Implementation*, the authors find that one large shortcoming is the lack of clarity around effective strategies for character education implementation. “Without such common understanding, educators, scholars, and practitioners alike will be led in many directions, which may or may not result in development of positive ‘character’.” (Bajovic, Rizzo, & Engemann, 2009, p. 17). However, Bajovic et al. may also give the solution concluding with one of their recommendations that all stakeholders should engage in meaningful discussion and reflection around character, morals, and values. In *The Handbook of Moral and Character Education*, the second of their “4 Keys” is *Self-Study*: a processes by which students self-assess their strengths and areas for growth (Davidson, Lickona, & Khmelkov, 2008). The Character Education Partnership’s *11 Principles of Character Education* lists student reflection under the second

principle, “The school defines ‘character’ comprehensively” (Lickona, Schaps, & Lewis, 2010, p.4).

With strong research supporting that “soft skills” support academic achievement, and that these skills can be encouraged through discussion and reflection, we therefore chose to focus on the skill of self-reflection and self-study regarding character traits and dispositional skills.

Method

Research Design

To answer our research question, we designed and implemented an action research intervention study using a pre-test post-test design. The dependent variables were academic achievement and attitude in math and art class. The independent variable was student self-reflection using a learner development matrix. We also had an attribute variable of gender and extraneous variable of prior ability in each content area. Our hypothesis was that if students spent class time self-reflecting on dispositional skills that lead to success in math and art, we would then see an increase in formal assessment scores.

Intervention

The intervention occurred in two math classes and two art classes over six weeks. Students in the treatment group were given class time to write journal reflections based on guided questions derived from the American School of Dubai middle school’s Learner Development Rubric (see Appendix D, Appendix E, and Appendix F). Both the control group and the treatment group were taught the same lessons and given the same formal assessments at the end of each unit.

Sample

The sample used in this study was a convenience sample of forty-two math students and forty-one art students at the sixth grade level. The class sizes vary from nineteen to twenty-three and the students are of mixed ability. All students in this study attend the American School of Dubai, in Dubai, United Arab Emirates.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

This study used a two-group pre/post test design to gather information regarding student achievement and attitude in math and art class. Student confidence and attitude were measured before and after using a Likert Scale Survey entitled, *Benedict's How I Feel About This Class* (see Appendix B). This ten-item survey had students respond to such statements as “This is my favorite class,” and “I am good at this class.” Students were asked to respond by either choosing “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Disagree,” or “Strongly Disagree,” and these values were associated with a point score of 4, 3, 2, or 1 respectively. Scores were totaled and gain scores were compared between the treatment and control groups.

Academic achievement was measured using formal assessment averages in both the treatment and control groups. The American School of Dubai uses standard based reporting where student grades are reported numerically based on curriculum standards (see Appendix C). Each content area has approximately five reporting strands that appear on the report card. Math pre-intervention scores were gathered from finding the means of the reporting strands on each student’s quarter 2 report card. Math post-intervention scores were gathered from strand means of each student’s quarter 3 report card.

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Since Art is only a quarter long class, previous quarter grades were not available. Instead, we used the first formal project assessment as the pre-intervention test and the last formal project assessment as the post-intervention test. Gain scores from academic achievement scores were compared between the treatment and control groups.

Threats to Validity

The greatest threat to validity is content threat. In Math class, quarter three is the only quarter that focuses on algebraic skills, where the other quarters focus on calculation and algorithmic skills. In Art class, as the projects continue, the technical skilled required is increased. Many of the student scores will be affected by aptitude and prior knowledge within those content areas.

We also needed to be wary of researcher bias. Inadvertently, we the researchers may influence the study by assisting the achievement of the treatment group, or we may subconsciously assess differently since many grades are subjective. Other threats to consider are: subject characteristics, we have seventy nationalities represented at our school and a mix of genders, both of which may effect learning; mortality, we had a few students leave the school during the study and were unable to complete the post-Likert Scale assessment; and finally repeated testing threat since we re-used the same Likert Scale Survey for both the pre and post treatment evaluations.

Results

Data was gathered, gain scores were calculated, and t-test analyses were used to examine group differences.

Student Attitude & Confidence

A two-tailed, unpaired, t-test showed no significant change in student attitude after receiving the treatment of guided reflection when compared to classes not receiving guided reflection (Math: $t = 1.1743$, $df = 39$, $P = 0.2478$; Art: $t = 1.0284$, $df = 37$, $P = 0.3101$). Table 1 shows the means and standard deviations of the change scores for each group.

Table 1

Means and Standard Deviations of Change Scores for Attitude & Confidence

	Math Reflection	Math Control	Art Reflection	Art Control
Change Mean	-0.357	0.891	-1.263	-2.364
Change SD	2.501	3.918	3.413	3.42

Figure 1 and Figure 2 below provides a visual representation of the mean score for student attitude and confidence comparing the treatment groups to the control groups.

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Figure 1. Visual representation of group means in student confidence and attitude in math class.

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Figure 2. Visual representation of group means in student confidence and attitude in art class.

Student Academic Achievement

The following discusses the results of each group on academic achievement markers.

Academic Achievement in Math. The results of the analysis of achievement on formal assessments in math class showed that the comparison between the group who did guided reflection and the control group showed no significance ($t = 1.2010$, $df = 39$, $P = 0.2370$).

Table 2

Means and Standard Deviations of Change Scores between quarter 3 and 2 marks in math

	Guided Reflection Group	Control
Mean	-0.199	-0.019
SD	0.469	0.491

Figure 3 below provides a visual representation of mean scores of final quarter reports in math class comparing the group who used guided reflection and the group who did not.

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Figure 3. Reflection group vs. control group grades compared between quarters 2 and 3 reports.

Academic Achievement in Art. The results of the analysis of achievement on formal assessments in art class showed that the reflection group’s academic achievement fared better significantly ($t = 2.2583$, $df = 37$, $P = 0.0299$). The means and standard deviations are shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Means and Standard Deviations of Change Scores between first and last assessment marks in art

	Guided Reflection Group	Control
Mean	-0.117	-0.4944

SD	0.5671	0.4748
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Figure 4 below provides a visual representation of mean scores of project assessment in art class comparing the group who used guided reflection and the group who did not.

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Figure 4. Reflection group vs. control group grades compared between projects 1 and 2 in art.

Discussion and Action Plan

The results of this study show that while reflection had no effect on attitude, confidence, or math achievement, it did however improve art assessments with statistical significance. In both subject areas, mean scores decreased from the pre- to post-tests, due likely to the increase of difficulty as the quarter progressed, however, the treatment group in art decreased comparatively less. This leads us to believe that if students are given dedicated class time to reflect on their own dispositions and character, they will score better on formal assessments in art class.

One of the large reasons we believe in the success of the art results is the direct correlation of the treatment to the reporting standards. When students are graded on formal assessments in art class, the grades are reported on ten reporting standards and three of them are related to self-reflection of their work. We believe the extra time spent reflecting in class then acted as practice for the assessments. In math class however, none of the strands we report on deal with self-reflection. Also, from in-class informal observations, the “soft skills” that seem to

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be the most helpful for a math assessment are algorithmic thinking and attention to detail – not self-reflection.

Moving forward, we therefore have three recommendations: Firstly, we believe in the principle of “specificity” – that you should spend your time teaching skills that correlate to your learner objectives. Secondly, as an extension of specificity, we believe that only the dispositional skills that align to learner objectives of a particular content area should be taught within the content class to allow for more time to specifically address the needed learner objectives. Other skills should be taught in dedicated study skills classes and character education programs. Lastly, schools should have a dedicated character/dispositional education program to teach the shared values of the community. It has been a critical part of our philosophy of education and the meta-analyses give clear evidence that Character Education and Study Skills programs lead to improved learning and achievement (Hattie, J. 2009).

It is important to implement these programs effectively to reap the academic rewards cited in the research. An unsuccessful strategy we see often employed is an exercise described by Alfie Kohn known as “‘If It’s Tuesday, This Must Be Honesty.’ [Where] one value after another is targeted, with each assigned its own day, week or month. This seriatim approach is unlikely to result in a lasting commitment to any of these values,” (Kohn, 1997, p. 430). Instead we should look to our teachers to know their content areas and which skills are worthwhile for meeting learner objectives, and we should look to recognized programs and resources rather than invention.

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Appendix A

American School of Dubai's Learner Development Matrix

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Positive Learning Attitude	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely
Identifies strengths and weaknesses as a learner Seeks/accepts challenge and copes well with change Demonstrates independence Demonstrates persistence in pursuit of excellence Demonstrates problem solving skills			
Organization and Time Management	3	2	1
Respects timelines Uses time efficiently Follows guidelines Completes work with care/conscientiousness Demonstrates organization and self-management			
Collaboration & Participation	3	2	1
Participates enthusiastically Listens actively Respects group goals Works to resolve conflict			
Core Values in Action	3	2	1
Assumes responsibility for decisions and behavior Respects ASD's Expectations and Code of Conduct Demonstrates integrity and honesty in academic work Demonstrates integrity and honesty in dealing with others Seeks to be of service to others Treats others with compassion and understanding			

Likert Scale Survey

Name:	
Grade:	Age:

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Class:				
Benedict's How I Feel Bout This Class				
Directions: Please circle the response that best describes how you feel about this class				
1. This is my favorite class	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
2. This class is easy for me.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
3. When I am faced with a problem in this class, I can always overcome it.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
4. I always enjoy dealing with the type of problems in this class.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
5. I know what I need to do in this class to be successful.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
6. I always understand what we are doing in class.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7. I can always talk about what we are doing in class with others.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
8. I always participate in class discussions.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
9. I know I will do well in this class without help from the teacher.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
10. I am good at this class.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree

Appendix C

Example report card showing strand grades in math class at the American School of Dubai.

Academic Achievement	Sem 2
RATIOS AND PROPORTIONAL RELATIONSHIPS	Ex
THE NUMBER SYSTEM	Pro
EXPRESSIONS AND EQUATIONS	Lim
GEOMETRY	Ade
STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY	N/A

Appendix D

Guided reflection questions used with the math treatment group.

Week#	Math Reflection:
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1	Semester 1 Reflection: Look at the Learner Development Rubric and pick a skill to improve. Give reasons on why that skill would help you and give methods you'll try to employ to develop that skill
2	Learner Development: Organization & Management - How do you feel you've been at not-taking in class? (are you good at summarizing? Are you slow? Are you efficient? Are you lazy? etc...) And are you notes useful? Do you use them after you've written them down? How do you use them?
3	Learner Development: Collaboration & Participation - Give two or three examples of how you "listen actively" in math class. Give one or two examples of how you could improve on your listening skills.
4	Learner Development: Pursuit of Excellence - How did you feel you prepared for the last test? Give evidence to support what you did or did not do. If you could go back in time, what would you change (if anything) about your studying?
5	Learner Development: Positive Learning Attitude - When you did your homework this weekend, how did the new organization procedure help you? Did you find it easier or harder? Why?
6	Learner Development: Quarter 3 Reflection - looking at the learner development rubric, with which skill did you find you were particularly successful? What would you like to continue to build on that success?

Appendix E

Guided reflection questions used with the art treatment group.

Week	Reflection
1	<p>Positive Learning Attitude: I showed independence and persistence when solving problems.</p> <p>1. Did you show this, this week in art? How or how not?</p>

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2	<p>Organization and Time Management: This week how did you or did you not do the below <u>in art</u>? Give Examples.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. I used work time efficiently.2. I completed my work with care, not just to get it done.
3	<p>Core Values in Action: I took responsibility for my choices and for my materials.</p> <p>Did you show this, this week in art? How or how not?</p>
4	<p>Core Values in Action: This week in art how did you or did you not do the below? <u>Give Examples.</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. I treat others with compassion and understanding?2. I seek to help others and clean up after myself?
5	<p>Reflect on the one learner development skill you chose to focus on at the end of last week.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. How did you or did you not meet this disposition? Give examples.
6	<p>Positive Learning Attitude: I attempted to challenge myself.</p> <p>How did you or did you not show this, this week in art?</p>

Appendix F

Example reflection on a student's eportfolio

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar displaying "https://sites.google.com/a/asdubai.org/aliza-qureshi-g6/...". The page content includes:

- Art:** An image of a paintbrush with a red handle and a rainbow-colored brush head.
- 6B, with Mrs. Benedict -**
- Positive Learning Attitude:** I showed independence and persistence when solving problems.
- 1) Did you show this, this week? How or how not?**
- Reflection:** I believe I showed independence and persistence when solving problems this week. Instead of asking Mrs. Benedict for help or a question, I asked a few of my peers that were at my table. I showed persistence by, when we were doing the drawing values and I thought I was doing something wrong, I kept trying until I got it right!

Transcription of the response above:

Positive Learning Attitude:

I showed independence and persistence when solving problems.

1) Did you show this, this week? How or how not?

I believe I showed independence and persistence when solving problems this week. Instead of asking Mrs. Benedict for help or a question, I asked a few of my peers that were at my table. I showed persistence by, when we were doing the drawing values and I thought I was doing something wrong, I kept trying until I got it right.